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Customer Satisfaction towards Online Shopping in Erode, Tamil Nadu, India

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Abstract:

Due to technological development and mechanical life of the people the online shopping is inevitable now a day. Online shopping or marketing is the use of technology (i.e., computer) for better marketing performance. And retailers are devising strategies to meet the demand of online shoppers; they are busy in studying consumer behavior in the field of online shopping, to see the consumer attitudes towards online shopping. It gives wide range of services to the consumers such as easy access, time saving in the buying activities, easy payment of prices over the online. It is very popular among the people whether, they are coming from urban area or rural area. This study attempted to find out the factors that influencing the consumer to use online shopping. The results are interpreted on the basis of data collected by using some statistical tools such as percentage analysis and ranking analysis.

[1]

Keywords: online shopping, online marketing, customer satisfaction, shopping behaviour

Introduction:

Online shopping is the process in which consumers directly buy goods, services etc. from a seller interactively in real-time without an intermediary service over the internet. Basically, online shopping is the process of buying goods and services from merchants who sell on the internet. Generally speaking, the trend of e-commerce has been increased rapidly in the recent years with the development of internet and due to the easy accessibility of internet usage. Online shopping is third most popular activity on the internet after email using and web browsing. Online shopping is used as a medium for communication and electronic commerce, to increase or improve in value, quality and attractiveness of delivering customer benefits and better satisfaction, that is why online shopping is more convenient and day by day increasing in popularity. E-commerce has been growing very fast because of many advantages associated with buying on internet, for example lower transaction and search cost as compared to other types of shopping. Through online shopping, consumers can buy faster, more alternatives are also available and can order product and services with comparative lowest price. It is also called as e-shop, online store, web-store and virtual shop. It has opened the doors to consumer and entrepreneurs to enter into the new electronic business world. Consumers are now using the online shops to make purchase of goods and services in a convenient way.

Problem Statement:

The online marketing has developed very well in last few years but also it also opens the pandora box to various difficulties to the consumers. The main problem that has led to make this research is online fraudulent activities, unsafe online environment, and its impact on consumer attitude and satisfaction.

Objectives of the Study:

Based on the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents, the objective of the paper is to:

1. determine the buying behavior of the respondents.
2. investigate the awareness level of the respondents about online marketing.
3. analyses the satisfaction level of the selected respondents.

Scope of the Study:

The scope of this study is extended as follows:

1. Analyze the socio-economic factors that influence the buying behavior of the respondents.
2. Identify the level of the awareness of the respondents and determine factors that attract consumers.
3. Determine the satisfaction level of the respondents from various perspectives such as on the basis of services provided, on the basis of features offered, etc.

Limitation of the Study:

1. The results of this study is only based on the data provided by the respondents.
2. Time availed for this study is limited, so the available tools are not used for the analysis.
3. The data are collected from only 50 respondents so the result may not be reliable, because the result of the whole population may vary.
4. The results are only relevant to Erode town.

Literature Review:

The usage of internet is at a high level in India. This is further driven by the rise in mobile phones and adoption of e-wallet in society. In fact, survey by Gartner quoted by Phutela and Altekhar (2019) evidence that smartphone users will exceed 500 million users by end of 2018. In fact, Phutela and Altekhar (2019) note that online shopping is attractive due to the convenience it presents but also presents problems related to making online payments. Gurāu (2008) note that phenomenon of transparency, interactivity and memory of the internet has given businesses the opportunity to have proactive-reactive attitude in [online communication](#), which is

important to attract customers and also create customization. Types of online communication may vary depending on the online store and types of products offered and target customers. Generally, the diverse global customers also need to be attended to be based on the language of communication. Many countries that request for local content to cater for their customers. According to Li (2011) [online marketing](#) should start focusing on niche marketing.

Childers, et al. (2001) argue that online shopping behavior needs to be studied to help create the correct interactive online webmosphere. Grange (2011) argues that customers are seeking new experiences in online shopping. He argues that the integration of social media and electronic commerce can create serendipity. In an age where people are looking for quick solutions, save time in physical space to ensure quality work and work-life balance, time for shopping is moving towards online shopping which also demands creative atmosphere to sustain the customers. According to Chen et al. (2019) product recommendations from trusted friends and also the presence of liking for a particular product will increase the possibility on effective online purchase. Thakur and Kaur (2019) concede that internet marketeers and e-commerce business strategists cannot ignore the non-metro city dwelling consumers as they have huge potential as future consumers.

Park and Kim (2003) demonstrate that online survey with 602 Korean customers of online bookstores give priority towards information quality, user interface quality, and security. This highly [influences the customer](#) towards commitment and actual purchase. Habeeb and Sudhakar (2019) note that e-service quality is very important to influence the purchase intent of online customers.

Research Methodology:

The method of research used in this study is descriptive research study, in which the data collected from the respondents, analyzed and on the basis of results description of the characteristics of a particular individual or group are made.

Sample size:

The sample is a part of the population that represents the whole population. The population of this research study is indefinite and sample size is 50 respondents in Erode, Tamil Nadu.

Sampling Design:

The technique used for selecting the individual item from the population is called as sample design. In this research work respondents are selected as a sample by using the convenient sampling method. It is a sampling method in which samples are collected on the basis of the researcher's convenience.

Collection and type of data:

Data are collected from the sample respondents by using interview schedule. The collected data are purely primary in nature i.e. collected afresh from the respondents.

Statistical tools used:

The data collected are analyzed by using the percentage analysis and ranking analysis. These are the methods widely used in the descriptive research study.

Data Analysis and Discussion:

Socio-Economic Profile of the Respondents:

From the selected respondents 11 (22%) respondents are up to 20 years of age group, 25 (50%) of the respondents are comes under the age group of 21-35, 14 (28%) of the respondents are above 36 years of age group. Among the 50 respondents 36 (72%) are male and 14 (28%) are female. 31 (62%) of the sample respondents are living in village and remaining 19 (38%) respondents are living in town. 43 (86%) of the sample respondents are belonging to nuclear family and 7 (14%) of the respondents are belonging to joint family. 26 (52%) of the respondents are completed post graduate study, 19 (38%) of the respondents are undergraduate and 5 (10%) respondents are having educational qualification as school level. From the selected respondents 24 (48%) of the respondents are student, 8 (16%) of the respondents are doing business and 18 (36%) of the respondents are belongs to profession. 4 (8%) of the respondents are earning below Rs. 5,000 pm, 13 (26%) of the respondents are earning Rs. 5001-10000, 19 (38%) of the respondents are earning Rs. 10001-20000 and 14 (28%) of the respondents earning is above Rs. 20,000.

Awareness and Online Shopping:

The Table 1 below shows the various online shopping patterns of the respondents.

Table 1: Awareness and Online Shopping a Buying Behavior of the Respondents

Basis	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Type of Portal used	Amazon	21	42
	Flipkart	12	24
	Snapdeal	6	12
	Olx	2	4
	Ebuy	5	10
	Others	4	8
	Total	50	100
Sources of Awareness	Friends	17	34
	Relatives	4	8
	Television	7	14
	Online advertisement	22	44
	Total	50	100
Type of product purchased	Computers	5	10
	Mobile Phones	26	52
	Electronics	11	22
	Books	6	12
	Cosmetics	2	4
	Total	50	100
Reasons for online shopping	Reasonable price	10	20
	Convenience	22	44
	Best services	4	8
	Time saving	14	28
	Total	50	100

Source: Field Survey

It is observed from the above Table 1, 21 (42%) of the sample respondents are using Amazon for their online shopping, 12 (24%) of the respondents are using Flipkart, 6 (12%) of the respondents are using Snapdeal, 2 (4%) of the respondents are using Olx, 5 (10%) of the respondents are using EBuy, 4 (8%) of the respondents are using other online shopping portals for their purchases.

On the basis of sources of awareness, 17 (34%) of the respondents came to aware about the online shopping through friends, 4 (8%) of the respondents got awareness through relatives, 7 (14%) of the respondents got awareness through the Television, and 22 (44%) of the respondents came to aware through online advertisements about the online shopping portals.

It is clear from the above table 5 (10%) of the respondents are using online shopping portals for buying computers, 26 (52%) of the respondents are using online shopping portal for buying Mobile phones, 10 (20%) of the respondents are using online shopping portals for buying electronics, 3 (6%) of the respondents are using online shopping for purchasing cosmetics.

On the basis of reasons of using online shopping, 10 (20%) of the respondents are using online shopping due reasonable price of the products available online, 22 (44%) of the respondents are using online shopping due its convenience, 4 (8%) of the respondents are using due to best services provided by the online shopping portals, 14 (28%) of the respondents are using online shopping because of it saves lot of time of the people.

Satisfaction Level of the Respondents:

The following Table 2 shows the satisfaction level of the respondents in Erode towards online shopping.

Table 2: Satisfaction Level of the Respondents

Details of Satisfaction	Satisfied		Neutral		Dissatisfied	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
Services Provided	13	26	24	48	13	26
Price of the product	29	58	12	24	9	18
Facilities available	11	22	31	62	8	16
Product quality	24	48	15	30	11	22
Product availability	15	30	26	52	9	18
Mode of Payment	18	36	17	34	15	30
After sales service	12	24	9	18	29	58
Total	122	35	134	38	94	27

Source: Field Survey

Note: F - frequency count

% - percentage

From the Table 2 given above it is clear that on the basis of the services provided 13 (26%) of the respondents are satisfied, 24 (48%) of the respondents are neutral and 13 (26%) of the respondents are dissatisfied. From the point of view of the price of the products offered on the online shopping portals, 29 (58%) of the respondents are satisfied, 12 (24%) of the respondents are neutral and 9 (18%) of the respondents are dissatisfied. On the basis of facilities available 11 (22%) of the respondents are satisfied, 31 (62%) of the respondents are neutral and 8 (16%) of the respondents are dissatisfied. On the basis of quality of the product offered on the online shopping portal, 24 (48%) of the respondents are satisfied, 15 (30%) of the respondents are neutral and 11 (22%) of the respondents are dissatisfied. Product availability as the basis of satisfaction level, 15 (30%) of the respondents are satisfied, 26 (52%) of the respondents are neutral and 9 (18%) of the respondents are dissatisfied. On the basis of mode of payment provided by the online shopping concerns, 18 (36%) of the respondents are satisfied, 17 (34%) of the respondents are neutral and 15 (30%) of the respondents are dissatisfied. Finally, on the basis of after sales services rendered by the online shopping sites, 12 (24%) of the respondents are satisfied, 9 (18%) of the respondents are neutral

and 29 (58%) of the respondents are dissatisfied. By sum up all, 38% of the respondents are neutral, 35% of the respondents are satisfied and 27% of the respondents are dissatisfied with the online shopping.

Problems Faced by the Respondents:

The Table 3 below shows the various problems or challenges encountered by the respondents when using online shopping.

Table 3: Problems Faced by the Respondents

Problem Faced	Rank - I (score=5)	Rank - II (score=4)	Rank - III (score=3)	Rank - IV (score=2)	Rank - V (score=1)	Total Mean Score
Product Differences	11	20	7	6	6	3.48
Online frauds	8	9	13	16	4	9.58
Quality differences	10	5	14	8	13	9.74
Delay in delivery	5	12	14	8	11	10.26
Network problem	3	4	2	33	8	8.86
Non-Availability of the product	12	11	16	5	6	6.5
Total	62	61	56	76	45	

Source: Field Survey

On the basis of problems faced by the respondents, 11 respondents gave 1st rank to product differences, 20 respondents gave 2nd rank for product differences 7 respondents gave 3rd rank to the product differences, 6 respondents gave 4th rank to the product differences and 6 respondents gave 5th rank to the product differences. Online frauds as a basis, 8 respondents gave 1st rank to online frauds, 9 respondents gave 2nd rank for online frauds 13 respondents gave 3rd rank to the online frauds, 16 respondents gave 4th rank to the online frauds and 4 respondents gave 5th rank to the online frauds. For quality differences, 10 respondents gave 1st rank, 5 respondents gave 2nd rank, 14 respondents gave 3rd rank, 8 respondents gave 4th rank and 13 respondents gave 5th rank. For delay in delivery, 5 gave 1st rank, 12 gave 2nd rank, 14 gave 3rd rank, 8 gave 4th rank and 11 gave 5th rank. For network connection problems, 3 respondents gave 1st rank, 4 respondents gave 2nd rank,

2 respondents gave 3rd rank, 33 respondents gave 4th rank, 8 respondents gave 5th rank. Non-availability of the product as a problem, 12 respondents gave 1st rank, 11 respondents gave 2nd rank, 16 respondents gave 3rd rank, 5 respondents gave 4th rank and 6 respondents gave 5th rank. Based on the total mean score, the most problematic issue is delay in delivery followed by quality differences of the products from the claims in the website. Respondents are least concerned about product differences followed by non-availability of the product.

Findings:

Demographic Details:

The socio-economic characteristics of the respondents are as described here. Majority 25 (50%) of the respondents are within the age group of 21-35 years of age. This is the prime age of internet users. Majority 36 (72%) of the respondents are male, while majority 31 (62%) of the respondents are residing in the village. This in the current phenomenon of many developing countries, whereby physical space is not an issue and the internet is heavily relied upon to bring people together and also to make shopping decision. A majority 43 (86%) of the respondents are belongs to the nuclear family also describing the current pattern of the households in India that are young families that are having nuclear families as they reside further from their immediate or extended families.

As per their education level, the majority 26 (52%) of the respondents have completed post graduate studies. While the balance 24 (48%) of the respondents are students. The level of education in India is generally high. A total of 19 (38%) of the respondents' earning is Rs. 10,001-Rs. 20,000 per month. (Note: Rs. 100 is equivalent to RM5.90)

Awareness About Online Shopping:

Majority 21 (%) of the respondents use Amazon for their online purchases. A total of 22 (44%) of the respondents got awareness through the online advertisements. Majority 30 (60%) of the respondents are using online shopping portals for purchasing mobiles, followed by electronics and books. Majority 22 (44%) of the respondents reported that they are using online shopping due to its convenience followed by time saving and cheaper pricing.

Satisfaction Level of the Respondents:

The satisfaction level of using the online shopping as reported by the respondents are noted as the following sentences. Majority 24 (48%) and 31 (62%) of the respondents are neutral to the services provided by the various portals and to the facilities provided by the online shopping sites. Majority 29 (58%) and 24 (48%) of the respondents are satisfied with the price of the products offered online and the quality of the products offered on the online shopping sites. A total of 18 (36%) of the respondents are satisfied with the mode of payment. While a large majority 29 (58%) of the respondents are dissatisfied with the after sales services. This is something that online stores should be aware of as many customers once they do not get feedback or after sales services, chances are they will not return to the site for further purchases.

Problems Faced by the Respondents:

The ranking of problems encountered by the respondents are shown in this section. Majority 20 respondents rated 2nd rank for the product differences. Only a total of 16 respondents scored 4th rank to online frauds. Majority 14 respondents gave 3rd rank to the quality differences and the delay in delivery respectively. A big majority 33 respondents gave 4th rank to the network problems. A total of 16 respondents gave 3rd rank to the non-availability of the products.

Suggestions:

The online shopping businesses should concentrate on the young people because the majority of the users are under the age group of 21-35 years. This could also be due to the type of products and services offered online currently. Considering the fact that the world is moving towards an ageing population, focus on elderly customers can be done based on elderly needs products.

Quality assurance of products is important to ensure customer loyalty and increased sales. Online shopping malls' consumers are dissatisfied that products displayed on the portal and actual products delivered are in different in nature.

Timely delivery service of products is also important to ensure that customers are not redirected to other competitive online sellers.

Online business can be varied based on the cohort of population addressed as potential customer. Demographic details based on age group, gender, ethnicity and religion may require specific products and services besides the general public that have common goods and services to purchase.

Fraudulent experiences will deter repeat purchase or return to the same online store. Therefore, assurance of secure online transactions is of utmost importance. This will include identity and payment details security.

Online malls also need to focus on after sales services to ensure queries and grievances are addressed accordingly and quickly. Customers who are unsatisfied with a purchase will need to know how they can return the goods and get refunds or if there are any discounts, etc.

Conclusion:

This study mainly attempted to analyze the awareness and satisfaction of the consumers of the online shopping in Erode, India. This study has revealed that most of the consumers want to make secure online transactions, get the quality products at right time and right place as experienced in the conventional physical stores. The main suggestion made in this study is that the firms need to concentrate on after sales services because most of the online shopping portals are lacking in the after sales services. Besides that, online stores also need to ensure that marketing and promotional strategies are customized to local customers. So, it is concluded that if online shopping stores concentrate on these issues a very big consumer base can be created more effectively.

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